

Voltage Profile and Stability Enhancement in Electrical Power System Using Improved Driving Training Based Optimization Algorithm

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ABSTRACT:

Voltage profile and stability are fundamental components of power system operation, guaranteeing the stable and efficient distribution of electrical energy to customers. The voltage profile is represented by the Voltage Deviation index (VD), which quantifies the difference between the measured voltage and the nominal voltage. A poor profile indicates that the lines are overloaded or that reactive power compensation is insufficient. Voltage stability is represented by the stability index (L-index), which measures the safe distance between the current operating point and the voltage collapse point. The goal of this paper is to find the best control variables (power and voltage magnitude of PV bus, Transformer tap settings, and shunt VAR compensation), in first case, for improving voltage profile, and in second case, for voltage stability enhancement in power grids. Improved Driving Training Based Optimization (IDTBO) algorithm is used for optimal power flow calculation. IDTBO is a metaheuristic algorithm inspired of driving training process, integrating Crowding Distance Technique and Levy Flight distribution. The methodology was tested on IEEE 30-bus system and the results were better than those obtained with the Modified Driving Training Based Optimization (MDTBO) algorithm cited in literature.

Keywords: Voltage Profile, Voltage Stability, Improved Driving Training Based Optimization, Crowding Distance, Levy Flight.

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INTRODUCTION

According to the "survey on voltage stability indices for power system transmission and distribution" by Baleboina GM and Mageshvaran R (2023), there are at least 90 types of voltage stability indices [1], this shows that voltage control is important for the proper functioning of an electrical network. In

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this paper, two voltage stability indices are used to optimize power transmission system: Voltage Deviation index (VD) introduced by Yang and al. (2012) [2], and L-index introduced by Kessel and al. (1986) [3]. These indices are voltage equations of transmission line-based bus indices that require a robust algorithm to solve. In the literature, modified version of original Driving Training Based Optimization algorithm, called MDTBO, is used by O. M. Ranarison and al. (2025) [4] to optimize these two objective functions. An improved version of this algorithm inspired of driving training process (IDTBO), recently proposed by Daniel Kwegyir and al. (2024) [5], using Levy Flight and Crowding Distance techniques, is proposed to solve optimal power flow (OPF) equation in this article.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main idea of OPF problem is to find best control variables for optimizing objective function while considering all the constraints of the power system (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Main Idea of OPF Problem

The inequality constraints are the limits of control and dependent variables, where:

P_{G1} : active power output at slack bus;

P_{Gi} : active power generation at the PV bus i except at the slack bus;

V_{Li} : voltage magnitude at PQ bus i ;

V_{Gi} : voltage magnitude at PV bus i ;

Q_{Gi} : reactive power output of generator unit i ;

Q_{Ci} : shunt VAR compensation at bus i ;
 S_{Li} : transmission line loading for line i ;
 T_i : tap setting of transformer for line i ;
 NPQ : number of load buses;
 NG : number of generator units;
 NTL : number of transmission lines;
 NC : number of VAR compensators;
 NT : number of regulating transformers.

The equality constraints require that the power injected into each bus ($P_{inj,i}, Q_{inj,i}$) be strictly equal to the generated (P_{Gi}, Q_{Gi}) and load power (P_{Li}, Q_{Li}).

In alternative current (AC-OPF), active and reactive power injected into each bus depend on the network admittance matrix:

$$Y_{bus} = G + jB \quad (1)$$

$$P_{inj,i} = |V_i| \sum_{j=1}^N |V_j| (G_{ij} \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j) + B_{ij} \sin(\theta_i - \theta_j)) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{inj,i} = |V_i| \sum_{j=1}^N |V_j| (G_{ij} \sin(\theta_i - \theta_j) - B_{ij} \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j)) \quad (3)$$

The load data are known and considered constant in the static analysis of the power transmission system.

Voltage Profile Improvement

In this case, Voltage Deviation index is used and given by:

$$VD = \sum_{i=1}^{NPQ} |V_i - 1| \quad (4)$$

VD represent the total of margin between the measured voltage and nominal voltage (1 p.u) of load buses. Objective is minimizing VD (best value is 0):

$$obj(VD) = \min (VD) \quad (5)$$

Voltage Stability Enhancement

It is represented by voltage stability index (L-index):

$$L_j = \left| 1 - \sum_{i=1}^{NPV} F_{ij} \frac{V_i}{V_j} \right| \quad (6)$$

Where : $j = 1, 2, \dots, NPQ$

F_{ij} is the i-th row and j-th column of matrix F:

$$F = -Y_{LL}^{-1}Y_{LG} \quad (7)$$

Elements of F are generated from admittance matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_L \\ I_G \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{LL} & Y_{LG} \\ Y_{GL} & Y_{GG} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_L \\ V_G \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Objective is to minimize the maximum value of L_j :

$$obj(L_{max}) = \min(\max(L_j)) \quad (9)$$

Where: $\max(L_j)$ is the weakest bus of the system.

Best value is near 0, no load case is 0, and collapse case is 1.

IDTBO Algorithm

IDTBO is a mix of three methods: Driving Training Based Optimization algorithm (DTBO), Levy Flight distribution, and Crowding Distance technique. Below are the steps for implementing this algorithm.

- 1- First step is to input options of the problem, set value of max iteration T and number of populations N
- 2- Second step is to initialize the population matrix using Levy Flight:

$$X_{ij} = x_{ij} + rand(A, D) \cdot levy(A) \quad (10)$$

$$x_{ij} = lb_j + (ub_j - lb_j) \cdot rand(A, D) \quad (11)$$

Where A and D are respectively the number of search agents and the dimension of the problem, ub_j and lb_j the upper and lower bounds of the solution.

Then calculate the initial value of the objective function as:

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} F_1 \\ \vdots \\ F_i \\ \vdots \\ F_N \end{bmatrix}_{N \times 1} = \begin{bmatrix} F(X_1) \\ \vdots \\ F(X_i) \\ \vdots \\ F(X_N) \end{bmatrix}_{N \times 1} \quad (12)$$

3- Third step consists of repeating the crowding distance method and the three phases of DTBO for N populations and for T iterations. The best solution is recorded at each iteration.

Objective function is updated as:

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} F(X_{best}) \\ \vdots \\ F(X_i) \\ \vdots \\ F(X_{worst}) \end{bmatrix}_{N \times 1} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{max} \\ \vdots \\ F_i \\ \vdots \\ F_{min} \end{bmatrix}_{N \times 1} \quad (13)$$

Then, the crowding distance of each member is calculated:

$$d_i = \frac{F_{i+1} - F_{i-1}}{F_{max} - F_{min}} \quad (14)$$

Update Driving Instructor (DI) matrix as: Instructor are the top half members of the population with the highest crowding distance, and learners are the other half.

Finally, start the three phases of DTBO: Training by the driving instructor, Patterning of the instructor skills of the student driver, Personal practice [6].

IEEE 30-Bus System

Buses data and lines data of IEEE 30-bus power system in [4] are used. There are nine shunt VAR compensations, at buses 10, 12, 15, 17, 20, 21, 23, 24, 29, four transformer tap settings, and six generators (Fig. 2). Total of active and reactive power load are 283.40 MW and 126.20 MVAR.

Figure 2. IEEE 30-Bus System with Shunt VAR Compensations

RESULTS

The program is run on MATLAB and results are obtained with the same machine as in [4]. Below are the variations of cost and VD with IDTBO compared to MDTBO, where objective function is improving voltage deviation.

Figure 3. Variations of Cost and Voltage Deviation with IDTBO – Objective (VD)

Figure 4. Variations of Voltage Deviation with IDTBO and MDTBO – Objective (VD)

Voltage magnitudes of 30 bus for case voltage deviation minimization obtained with IDTBO are compared with MDTBO and initial case without optimization, in Figure 5.

In case where objective function is voltage stability enhancement, cost and Lmax variations with IDTBO are presented in Figure 6. Lmax variation with IDTBO is compared to MDTBO in Figure 7.

30 bus system voltage profiles with IDTBO for objective voltage profile improvement are compared to objective voltage stability enhancement in Figure 8.

Active and reactive power flow and losses through transmission lines with IDTBO and MDTBO for the two objective functions are presented in Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11 and Figure 12. Optimal settings of power and voltage magnitude of PV bus, Transformer tap settings, and shunt VAR compensation, for the IEEE 30-bus system are listed in Table 1.

Figure 5. System Voltage Profiles for Objective (VD) with IDTBO and MDTBO

Figure 6. Variations of Cost and Voltage Deviation with IDTBO – Objective (Lmax)

Figure 7. Variations of Voltage Deviation with IDTBO and MDTBO – Objective (Lmax)

Figure 8. System Voltage Profiles for Objectives (Lmax) and (VD) with IDTBO

Figure 9. Active Power Flow through Transmission Lines with IDTBO, MDTBO – VD, Lmax

Figure 10. Active Power Losses through Transmission Lines with IDTBO, MDTBO – VD, Lmax

Figure 11. Reactive Power Flow through Transmission Lines with IDTBO, MDTBO – VD, Lmax

Figure 12. Reactive Power Losses through Transmission Lines with IDTBO, MDTBO – VD, Lmax

Table 1. Optimal Settings of Control Variables for IEEE 30-Bus System

Variables	Min	Max	Initial case	MDTBO (obj:VD)	IDTBO (obj:VD)	MDTBO (obj:Lmax)	IDTBO (obj:Lmax)
P_1	50	200	99.2225	174.3669	176.6139	155.9717	174.0222
P_2	20	80	80	48.5661	48.5047	47.6195	46.6509
P_5	15	50	50	21.1154	21.6017	25.3178	22.9485
P_8	10	35	20	21.2827	20.5224	26.5968	21.1071
P_{11}	10	30	20	13.5531	12.4406	17.0993	12.1605
P_{13}	12	40	20	14.2735	13.5452	18.1837	15.0595
V_1	0.95	1.1	1.0500	1.0397	1.0378	1.1	1.1
V_2	0.95	1.1	1.0400	1.0237	1.0227	1.0896	1.0867
V_5	0.95	1.1	1.0100	1.0143	1.0133	1.0876	1.0779
V_8	0.95	1.1	1.0100	1.0083	1.0046	1.0878	1.0881
V_{11}	0.95	1.1	1.0500	1.0141	1.0211	1.0903	1.0995
V_{13}	0.95	1.1	1.0500	0.9984	1.0041	1.0996	1.1
T_{11}	0.9	1.1	1.0780	0.9793	1.0073	0.9433	0.9588
T_{12}	0.9	1.1	1.0690	0.9272	0.9329	1.0084	0.9840
T_{15}	0.9	1.1	1.0320	0.9506	0.9605	1.0096	1.0193
T_{36}	0.9	1.1	1.0680	0.9582	0.9628	0.9553	0.9664
Q_{10}	0.0	5.0	0	2.4286	3.1993	4.9988	4.3067
Q_{12}	0.0	5.0	0	2.7292	1.9150	1.4813	3.8988
Q_{15}	0.0	5.0	0	3.3897	2.3611	1.9031	1.2373

Q_{17}	0.0	5.0	0	2.5774	2.2375	3.3039	2.8457
Q_{20}	0.0	5.0	0	2.3691	5	1.1050	3.6999
Q_{21}	0.0	5.0	0	4.5337	5	4.9856	4.9648
Q_{23}	0.0	5.0	0	5	4.9868	3.4176	3.8951
Q_{24}	0.0	5.0	0	1.3463	4.9974	0.2098	2.8785
Q_{29}	0.0	5.0	0	1.7527	1.9686	3.0800	4.9039
Cost (\$/h)			901.9501	804.1092	803.6454	805.3322	800.5364
P_{loss} (MW)			5.8225	9.8513	9.9243	7.3901	8.5500
Q_{loss} (MVAR)			-4.6063	11.4872	11.3572	-0.8028	3.4426
V_D			1.1496	0.1322	0.1119	1.8505	1.9151
Lmax			0.1723	0.1390	0.1372	0.1172	0.1151
Elapsed time (s)				177.8947	156.8232	177.1214	161.2811

DISCUSSION

In the first case where objective is voltage deviation minimization, VD index is the best with IDTBO (0.1119) compared to MDTBO (0.1322), as also presented in Figure 4. With no violation for the values of control variables (Table 1), results obtained with MDTBO (804.1092 \$/h) is more expensive than IDTBO (803.6454 \$/h). Cost is minimized with VD index as shown in Figure 3. In the initial case, there are some bus where voltage magnitude is under the minimal value (0.95 p.u), but with IDTBO, voltage profiles of all bus are greatly improved as with MDTBO (Fig. 5). In the second case where objective is voltage stability enhancement, Lmax is the best with IDTBO (0.1151) compared to MDTBO (0.1172) as shown in Figure 7, and greatly improved compared to the first case (0.1372). The total cost of all loads (800.5364 \$/h) is very interesting with IDTBO, compared to MDTBO (805.3322 \$/h). Cost is also minimized with the voltage stability index (Fig. 6). However, voltage profile is poor if objective is voltage stability enhancement (Fig. 8), which explains the high value of VD (1.9151). In the two cases, power flow and losses with IDTBO and MDTBO are very competitive (Fig. 9, Fig. 10, Fig.11, Fig. 12). But about speed, IDTBO algorithm is the best with 156.8232 seconds for VD case and 161.2811 seconds for Lmax case, compared to 177 seconds for cases with MDTBO.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, the IDTBO algorithm which is the combination of DTBO algorithm, Levy Flight distribution and Crowding Distance technique, is used in this study to improve two objective functions: Voltage Profile improvement, represented with voltage deviation index (VD), and Voltage Stability enhancement, represented with voltage stability index (L-index). Proposed method is tested with IEEE 30-bus system and the results show that IDTBO is more interesting than MDTBO cited in the literature. Objective functions are greatly improved, with a best cost and better calculation speed. However, it is conceivable, as a perspective, to consider a multi-objective function to improve both cases simultaneously.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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